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VOCATIONAL INTERESTS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF BAREILLY DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT: -

Vocational interests are related to the likeness one has for a particular job or vocation. This study examined the vocational interests of secondary school students. Through simple random sampling technique, a total sample of 240 students selected from Bareilly district. Vocational interests Record (VIR-K) developed by Dr. S.P. Kulshrestha (1977) was used for data collection. Data was analyzed by using percentage for each interest area. Findings showed that male participants showed higher vocational interests in the area of vocations as Literary, Scientific, Executive, and Commercial whereas female participants showed higher vocational interests in the area of vocations as Constructive and Household. It was also found that urban area school students showed higher interests in all vocational areas than rural area school students.

KEYWORDS: Vocational Interests, Secondary School Students.

INTRODUCTION :

Every child has unique mental ability and this ability tends towards the interest of child. Interest can be categorized as a force which motivates anyone to engage in specific work according to his or her ability, if guided or decided properly. Vocational interests means to take interest in any vocation, to pay attention, to get attracted and to be satisfied with it. Vocational interests are a none other than our mental attitude. It shows likes and dislikes towards certain vocations. From the educational, psychological and vocational view point, it is very essential to know the area of one's Vocational interests. The school should take up the responsibility of helping the child in the vocational sphere of his life, because occupation is not only a means of earning a livelihood but also a way of life a social life. Interest is motivation for the task and an important factor in achievement. It affords pleasure and satisfaction, creates enthusiasm and curiosity and strengthens vocational aspect of mind. It is the source of one's life routine and affects one's behavior. It results in full attention and concentration (Walia 1999).

VOCATIONAL INTERESTS

The term 'Vocational interests' is used with different meanings. It may mean interest in the occupation as a whole. It may mean pleasure in the activities of the occupation or it may even mean satisfaction in the job (Mohanty 2006). Kulshrestha (2005) defined Vocational interests as one's own pattern of preferences, attitudes, likes and dislikes, preferred in any manner, wisely or unwisely by self or by another sources for a given vocational areas or vocation. Vocational interests assessment has been widely used for many years to gauge and guide one's career path and match individuals to job (Perdue,

Reardon & Peterson, 2007; Savickas, 2011). Not only can vocational interests predict vocational choice, but they also serve as a critical lens to understand issues in various areas of psychology, including individual differences, individual development, gender difference in work preference, and more recently, job performance and turnover. According to Sharma (2013), Vocational choices are a developmental process and spans almost through person's lifetime. Vocational interests could be defined as a sequence of position jobs or occupation which a person engages in during working life.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Tomar (1985) investigated that boys had highest concentration on agriculture and lowest was on household whereas girls had highest concentration on fine arts and lowest was on medical areas. It was also found that urban students' highest concentration was on literary areas and lowest was on agriculture areas, and rural students' highest concentration was in the agriculture and lowest was on the medical areas. But Javed (1990) found that rural students were disinterested in agriculture and more interested in vocations connected with science.

Kumar (2017) observed that urban students were slightly more interested in literary, outdoor, executive and scientific fields. It was also found that rural students were slightly more interested in mechanical, business and agriculture fields than urban students.

Otta & Williams (2014) revealed that there was a significant relationship between self concept and vocational interests. It was also found that there was no significant difference between vocational interests of male and female students.

Singh (2014) found that girls were slightly more interested in literary, commercial, constructive, artistic, social and household areas. In the case of scientific, executive, agriculture and persuasive areas, boys were slightly more interested than that of girls.

Khandwala (2017) investigated that male students were more interested in enterprising fields of vocations than female students.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The most necessary demand of our country is to have vocationalization of our education system and to provide more and more vocational courses after secondary education according to the interest of students (Soundaravallia 2006). The current study would provide knowledge about current vocational interests of secondary school students. It may be helpful for students, teachers, parents and educational administrators in different ways like to understand current trends of vocation in market and to help students in selecting and pursuing career of their choice.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the vocational interests of male and female students.
- To study the vocational interests of urban and rural area school students.

METHODOLOGY

In the present study, descriptive survey method was used. The students studying in the class X of secondary schools located in the Bareilly district constitute the population. The sample of the present study was drawn from ten schools through random sampling technique. The total sample of the students was 240 consisting of 164 boys and 76 girls. Vocational interests Record (VIR-K) developed by Dr. S. P. Kulshrestha (1977) used for data collection. The VIR consists of 200 vocations belonging to the different vocational interests areas. The data collected from the sample was analyzed by using percentage. This is a qualitative interpretation of the data. The study was delimited to class X students affiliated to U.P. Board of Bareilly district only.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table-1: Vocational Interests of Male and Female Students

S.No.	Vocational Areas	Male (N=164)		Female (N=76)	
		Percentage	Rank	Percentage	Rank
1	Literary (L)	36.19	6	34.87	7
2	Scientific	49.76	2	44.34	3
3	Executive	56.74	1	48.42	1
4	Commercial	35.03	7	29.67	8
5	Constructive	20.58	10	21.78	10
6	Artistic	40.67	5	37.89	6
7	Agriculture	33.75	8	27.24	9
8	Persuasive	46.80	4	40.79	5
9	Social	48.87	3	45.59	2
10	Household	30.88	9	41.05	4
	Total	39.93		37.16	

From Table-1, it is revealed that the interest of male students in literary vocations was 36.19% whereas it was 34.87% for female students. The Literary vocation includes the jobs like Editor, Translator, Journalist, Writer and Language teacher etc. Findings revealed that the female students had less interest in literary vocations as compared to male students. The reason might be that females in Indian patriarchal society don't have freedom of expression which is essential for Literary Vocations.

The interest of male students in scientific vocations was 49.76 % whereas it was 44.34% for female students. The Scientific vocation includes the jobs like Engineers, Health officer, Scientist, Science teacher etc. The interest of male students in scientific vocation was found to be higher as compared to female students because male being a bread earner in Indian society, are facilitated to choose science background whereas girls are refrained to it.

The interest of male students in Executive vocations was 56.74% whereas it was 48.42% for female students. The Executive area includes the jobs like Civil Servants, Mayor of Corporation, Manager, Principal, Executives etc. Findings showed that male students are more interested in these areas because it provides luxurious and dominating life to them.

The interest of male students in commercial vocations was 35.03% whereas it was 29.67% for female students. The jobs included in the areas of Commercial interests are Typist, Secretary, Accountant, Draftsman, Salesman etc. Female students showed low interest in commercial vocations than male students because of male stereotyping in such professions.

The interest of male students in Constructive areas was 20.58% whereas it was 21.78% for female students. The constructive vocations include Dyer, Teacher of art & crafts, Designer etc. Findings project that female are more interested in these areas because females want to make their own image in the society.

The interest of male students in Artistic vocations was 40.67% whereas it was 37.89% for female students. The artistic jobs include, Singer, Music Director, Painter, Cartoonist, Sculptural etc. The reason for this might be that such jobs required lot of concentration and solitude which girls dislike generally.

The interest of male students in Agriculture vocations was 33.75% whereas it was 27.24% percent in

female students. This area is concerned with the assignment of Gardener, Farmer, Animal husbandry, Soil specialist, Horticulturist, Dairyman etc. Findings of the study showed that males are more interested in the agriculture area because this is a male oriented vocation.

The interest of male students in Persuasive vocations was 46.80% whereas it was 40.79% for female students. Persuasive jobs are full of persuasion. They are M.P., M.L.A., Insurance Agent, Vocational-Counselor, Ambassador, Advocate, Tourist-guide etc. Findings revealed that male are more interested in persuasive areas than female because of male stereotyping.

Findings of the study revealed that the interest of male students in social vocations was 48.87% whereas it was 45.59% for female students. Social jobs are Religious reformer, Red-Cross workers, Guide, Social worker etc. Male are more interested in these areas than female students because in Indian society it is not supposed to be prestigious job.

The interest of male students in Household vocations was 30.88% and it was 41.05% for female students. Household includes the job like Embroider, Home Science Teacher, Nurse, Home Manager, Cook etc. Findings showed that female students have more interest in these areas than male students because female bears all the household responsibility of the family.

Table-2: Vocational Interests of Urban and Rural Area School Students

S.No.	Vocational Areas	Urban area school students (N=120)		Rural area school students (N=120)	
		Percentage	Rank	Percentage	Rank
1	Literary	45.75	5	25.79	9
2	Scientific	52.37	2	43.70	3
3	Executive	59.50	1	48.71	1
4	Commercial	39.33	8	27.33	7
5	Constructive	28.29	10	13.62	10
6	Artistic	44.79	6	34.79	5
7	Agriculture	35.87	9	27.50	6
8	Persuasive	51.42	3	38.37	4
9	Social	49.87	4	45.83	2
10	Household	42.00	7	26.21	8
	Total	45.22		33.18	

From Table-2, it is revealed that interest of urban area school students in the Literary areas was 45.75% and it was 25.79% for rural area school students. Findings revealed that urban area school students are more interested in the literary vocation than rural area school students because they have better facility of learning and good exposure as compared to rural students.

The interest of urban students in the scientific vocations was 52.37% whereas it was 43.70% for rural students. Findings projects that rural students are less interested in scientific vocations as compared to urban students. The reason may be the economic status and lack of opportunities for rural students.

The interest of urban students in the Executive areas was 59.50% and it was 48.71% for rural students. Urban students are more interested in executive vocations because it will help them to attain the luxuries which they are used to.

It was also found that the interest of urban students in commercial vocations was 39.33% whereas it was 27.33% for rural students. Findings revealed that urban students have more interested in this vocation than rural students because of the reason that they are more and better educational opportunities.

The interest of urban students in constructive areas was 28.29% whereas it was 13.62% for rural students. Both urban and rural students showed less interest in constructive vocations but urban students have more interest in this area than rural students. The reason might be that these vocations require concentration, dedications and lot of time. Moreover the earning is also is very less as compared to other vocations.

The interest of urban students in Artistic areas was 44.79 % and it was 34.79% for rural students. The interest of urban students was more as compared to rural students because of better exposure of urban students.

The interest of urban students in Agriculture vocations was 35.87% and it was 27.50% for rural students. Findings projects that urban students are more interested in agriculture vocations because they have scientific attitude and have more exposures to take degree in such courses.

The interest of urban students in Persuasive areas was 51.42% whereas it was 38.37% for rural students. Findings revealed that urban students have more interest in persuasive areas than rural students because they are more inclined towards luxury and pomp & show.

The interest of urban students in Social vocations was 49.87% and it was 45.83% for rural students. Urban students showed more interest in social areas than rural students because of more awareness.

The interest of urban students in Household vocations was 42.00% whereas it was 26.21% for rural students. Urban students showed moderate interest in household whereas rural student showed less interest in this area because rural students consider this as a feminine area.

SUMMARY OF THE STUDY

The following was the main findings of the present study-

1. Male and female students both showed their first choice for executive vocational areas but male students' vocational interests was higher than female students in this area. Male students had second choice for scientific vocational areas but female students had second choice for social vocational areas. Male students' third choice was social and female students third choice was scientific vocational areas.
2. Urban and rural area school students both first choice was executive vocational areas, but urban school students' vocational interests for executive vocations was higher than rural area school students. Urban area school students' second choice was scientific vocations, and rural area school students' second choice was social vocations. Urban area school students' third choice was persuasive vocations and rural area school students' third choice was scientific vocations.

CONCLUSION

Male students showed their preference for vocational interests' viz., executive, scientific, social, persuasive, artistic, literary, commercial, agriculture, household, and lastly constructive vocational areas. Female students showed their preference for vocational interests' viz., executive, social, scientific, household, persuasive, artistic, literary, commercial, agriculture, and constructive vocations. Male students showed higher vocational interests in literary, scientific, executive, commercial, artistic, agriculture, persuasive, and social vocational areas than female students. Female students showed higher vocational interests in household and constructive vocational areas than male students. Urban area school students showed their preference for vocations respectively, executive, scientific, persuasive, social, literary, artistic, household, commercial, agriculture, and constructive vocational areas. Rural area school students showed their preference for vocations respectively executive, social, scientific, persuasive, artistic, agriculture, commercial, household, literary and constructive vocational areas. Urban and rural area school students both showed their first choice for executive vocational area. Urban area school students showed higher vocational interests in all ten vocational areas than rural area school students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Government should intensify effort to provide guidance counselors to secondary schools to provide vocational, educational and social guidance to the students, parents and teachers. Proper vocational guidance can be provided to the students on the basis of their interest for a particular vocation. This will increase their efficiency and motivation. There should be provision for tests and seminars for the students to increase their level of vocational interests.

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